

DIPLOMA

TA'LIM FIDOYILARI

RESPUBLIKA ILMIY JURNALIDA

L.Shamuratova

THE EPISODE OF MURATBAY NIZANOV'S ARTISTIC WORK "ASHIQ
BOLMAĞAN KIM BAR"

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

Bosh muharrir:
A.A. Abdurahmonov

2023/YANVAR

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MENTION

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